

CYCLIC BUCKLING AND POSTBUCKLING OF DAMAGED LAMINATED STRINGER STIFFENED COMPOSITE CYLINDRICAL PANELS

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SUMMARY

Test results obtained on laminated stringer stiffened composite cylindrical panels subjected to static and cyclic axial compression are presented. Some of the tested panels were pre-damaged in the vicinity of the stringers. The experimental results show that the tested specimen are not sensitive to damage and can be repeatedly buckled in deep postbuckling region without any degradation.

Keywords: Cyclic buckling, post-buckling region, damaged panels, cylindrical panels

INTRODUCTION

The performances of the air transport sector as a whole have almost reached a stage of leveling off. New breakthrough design concepts and technologies are needed to introduce a new era of air flight. Air transport demands are predicted to double in the next 10 – 15 years and triple in 20 years time. Involved with it, both the European and American aeronautical industries expect an operating cost reduction of 20% in the mean period followed by a further reduction of 50% in the long run [1].

These extreme expectations can be understood and realized based on the present traditional and future proposed COCOMAT design scenarios of basic aeronautical structures – a laminated composite stringer-stiffened panel, the axial compression load vs. end shortening behavior of which is depicted in Figure 1. This schematic figure summarizes the vision of the COCOMAT consortium: improved material exploitation of laminated composite airframe structures by accurate simulation of postbuckling and collapse [1-2].

It is clearly obvious from assessment of the various design parameters that are associated with Fig. 1, that among the attempts and solutions to achieve the above anticipations, narrowing the too large conservative gap traditionally accepted between the ultimate and the collapse load capacities should be considered as a challenge. Thus yielding the future lighter design scenario as depicted in Fig.1.

Fig. 1 Typical load vs. displacement curve of composite stiffened panels: present and future design scenarios.

To realize this target, it is necessary to develop the appropriate reliable tools, which are complemented and validated by a sound experimental data base to correctly and safely predict the behavior of a laminated composite stringer-stiffened shell in the "deep" postbuckling region and its collapse load, which is characterized by the probable following failure modes : separation between the skin and the stringers, delaminations, crack propagations and matrix failure, as well as to get better insight and understanding of the phenomena associated with its behavior under repeated buckling, particularly in the range of "deep" postbuckling loading. During its normal service life, a fuselage, which is composed of many curved laminated composite stringer-stiffened panels, may experience no more than a few hundreds of buckling-postbuckling cycles. Although it is well recognized that CFRP stiffened structures are capable of withstanding very deep postbuckling, yielding collapse loads that for certain configurations can be equal to three - four times and even more their buckling load (see for example Refs. [4-6]), scarce knowledge exists in the literature about the effects of repeated buckling on the global behavior of panels composing such fuselages. The data found in the literature is dealing with simple structures and loadings [7-8]. Very few results are available (for example [9-11]) on how repeated buckling under combined loading influences the non-linear behavior of aluminum cylindrical shells and CFRP aeronautical type panels and their collapse modes, and on how far into the postbuckling region it is possible to increase loading without losing structural integrity and consequently safety.

Considering structural degradation in the postbuckling region, a lot of aspects have to be taken into account. In the past years different failure criteria have been developed to evaluate initiation of degradation of structural integrity, as well as comprehensive failure, (see typical examples [12-13]). As a result of the COCOMAT effort, numerous manuscripts have been published on those issues (typical examples [14-15, 18-19]).

It seems that although a great deal of knowledge pertinent to the effect of damage has been accumulated, yet the influence of structural and material degradation due to static and low duration cycling loading on collapse of a stringer-stiffened panel has not been sufficiently investigated to reach viable and sufficient design reliability.

Therefore, in light of the above arguments, it is the aim of the present manuscript to contribute to the basic insight, understanding and knowledge of the phenomena related

to above topic and the factors that control it, by summarizing the Technion effort and share of the experimental and numerical results that were experienced and obtained within the COCOMAT consortium, during the years 2003-2008. Due to the limited space, only typical results of this extensive investigation will be presented. The extended results can be found in [20].

SPECIMENS AND TEST SET-UP

Within the framework of the COCOMAT effort, Israel Aircraft Industries (IAI) has designed and manufactured 16 Hexcel IM7 (12K)/8552(33%) graphite-epoxy stringer-stiffened composite panels, using a co-curing process. The nominal radius of each panel was $R=938$ mm and its total length $L=720$ mm (which included two loading pieces 30 mm height each). The nominal test length was $L_n=680$ mm and the panel arc-length was $L_{al}=680$ mm. The skin lay-up was of quasi-isotropic type $(0^\circ, \pm 45^\circ, 90^\circ)_S$. Each layer had a nominal thickness of 0.125 mm. All the panels were stiffened by blade type stringers, as presented in Fig. 2. To facilitate the manufacturing and reduce costs, as well as enhance possible initiation of skin-stringer separation, all the stringers except those corresponding to panel COCOMAT1 deliberately did not include the common practice drop-off plies at their base, that are normally introduced to avoid very high local stresses at the stringer base-skin interface as depicted in Fig. 2a. It has been assumed that the straight edges might lead to local stringer-skin separation that consequently will trigger comprehensive failure. To provide a reference point, the first panel COCOMAT1, was manufactured with drop-off plies (Fig. 2b) similar to some of the panels manufactured in the predecessor program POSICOSS [16].

Fig. 2 Dimensions, geometry and lay-ups of stringers forming: (a) Panels COCOMAT2-COCOMAT16, (b)- Panel COCOMAT1

All of the panels tested were stiffened by 5 blade type stringers. The panels, except COCOMAT5 and COCOMAT6, that were employed to construct torsion BOX A, which was used in another test program, were tested under axial compression only using the 50tons MTS loading machine at the Aerospace Structures Laboratory, Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Technion, I.I.T., Haifa, Israel .To visualize the buckling patterns and their development in postbuckling, the Moiré technique has been applied [16]. Strain gages were bonded back-to-back, both on the skin and on the stringers while lateral and axial LVDT's were used to monitor the out-of-plane deflections and the end-shortening, in response to the applied axial compression (for details see [3]).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The accompanied numerical predictions were performed using the ABAQUS Explicit code [16,17,20]. It was used to predict the "first" buckling load and the collapse load¹ carrying capability of the tested panels. Three panels, COCOMAT1, COCOMAT3 and COCOMAT4 were tested under repeated buckling. These panels were manufactured without initial damage. The first panel, COCOMAT1, as mentioned above, was stiffened by stringers similar to those used in the previous program, POSICOSS [16] (Fig. 2b). It was first loaded statically, to yield the "first" buckling at 70.9 kN equal to 0.785 of ABAQUS prediction buckling load (a single local wave) and a fully pattern of waves appeared at 84 kN (0.931 of ABAQUS prediction). It was then repeatedly buckled within a range of 0-120kN, which is equal to 1.331 ABAQUS "first" buckling prediction (fully developed surface) or 0.538 ABAQUS collapse prediction, with a frequency of 2Hz. This range was kept for the first 2k cycles, the requirement imposed by the COCOMAT project. The readings of the strain gages were recorded every 500 cycles. No reduction in the axial stiffening was observed. Then, the panel was again cycled for another 48k cycles to reach a total of 50k cycles within the range of 0-120 kN. Following, another 10k cycles were performed in the range of 0-150 kN, equal to 1.663 ABAQUS "first" buckling prediction, or 0.729 ABAQUS collapse prediction. Then, the panel was loaded till collapse at 216 kN, equal 1.050 ABAQUS collapse prediction (which compared well with the value obtained by panel PSC1, 212kN, which was of similar dimensions and properties [16]). The collapse load experienced in the tests was more than twice the buckling capacity corresponding to both "first" buckling and "first" buckling with a fully developed buckling surface. Almost an identical ratio was predicted by ABAQUS. This provides a higher margin between buckling and collapse than it is required by design, i.e. the panel is overdesigned, provided it meets limit load requirements. The collapse was characterized by breakage of fibers and tearing of the skin.

The next panel tested COCOMAT2, was stiffened by five stringers without drop-off layers (Fig. 2a). As mentioned above, this configuration was proposed by the COCOMAT project as a means to initiate skin-stringer debonding, either in the vicinity of collapse load or during cycling loading. The panel was loaded and unloaded under lower axial compression (less than 5kN) before starting the process till collapse. The panel buckled at 63.7kN (single localized wave) followed by a well formed pattern of waves under 88.2 kN (well compared with the load experienced by COCOMAT1 and the numerical value of 90.19kN predicted by ABAQUS Explicit [17]). It collapsed at 215.6kN (again well compared with COCOMAT1 and the numerical value of 205.8kN predicted by ABAQUS Explicit [17]). The collapse was accompanied by breakage of fibers of the stringer and the skin.

The very good correlation with the test results of COCOMAT1, designated as the reference panel indicates that the proposed modified configuration had no effect on either the load carrying capacity, buckling or collapse, or initiation of the anticipated load failure due to stringer base-skin separation at their interface. The load capacities, experimental and predicted, of COCOMAT2 are similar to those corresponding to COCOMAT1. Thus, the above discussion about the margin of loading between buckling and collapse applies to COCOMAT2 as well.

¹ The collapse load is defined as the load at which the stiffeners would buckle yielding the highest load sustainable by the stiffened panel

Panel COCOMAT3, a triplet of COCOMAT2, and COCOMAT4 was next tested under repeated buckling. It first statically buckled at 75.44kN (single wave). At 88.44kN three waves appeared, which is in excellent agreement with the buckling capacity of COCOMAT2 and ABAQUS prediction. Then, the panel was repeatedly cycled in a range of 0-147.5kN (1.632 buckling load and 0.715 collapse load predictions yielded by ABAQUS) during 2k cycles, without demonstrating any visible reduction in the axial stiffness. The panel completed 50k cycles within that load range, complemented by another 10k cycles in the range of 0-166.77kN (1.849 buckling and 0.910 collapse capacities computed with ABAQUS). Next the panel was tested till collapse, which occurred at 209.5 kN, again in very good agreement with COCOMAT2 and ABAQUS prediction.

COCOMAT4 was "first" statically buckled at 75.44kN (single wave) and almost a fully developed waves pattern was observed under 88.44 kN, which compares very well with the test results corresponding to COCOMAT2 and COCOMAT3, as well as with ABAQUS prediction. Next it was repeatedly cycled in the range of 0-147.5kN equal to 1.632 buckling and 0.715 collapse predicted by ABAQUS for 2k cycles, without noticeable reduction in the axial stiffness. The panel completed 50k cycles in that load range, then loading was complemented during another 10k cycles in the range of 0-176.58kN (corresponding to 1.958 buckling and 0.858 collapse predicted by ABAQUS) and another 2k cycles in the range 0-196kN (equal to 2.175 and 0.954 ABAQUS predictions). The panel was then tested till collapse, which occurred at 208 kN (in very good agreement with the results of COCOMAT2 and COCOMAT3 and ABAQUS calculations).

Following the above discussions and evaluation of the observations associated with the tests and calculations corresponding to panels COCOMAT1-COCOMAT4 it was found that subjecting of the above four panels to repeated buckling under loads ranging from 0.58 till 0.95 of their prescribed collapse load did not affect their postbuckling behavior. Note that one could have considered in the evaluation of the results the experimental observed collapse load, however because of the very good agreement of the test results with ABAQUS predictions there will be a minor difference between the above quoted range and that corresponding to the observed test results.

Damage is a major factor that has to be looked into in studying repeated loading of a structure, particularly when considering repeated buckling in relatively deep postbuckling range, where deformations are significantly large. To investigate the influence of damage on repeated buckling of the panels, another four panels were tested, COCOMAT 7 - COCOMAT 10. All of these panels contained local prescribed initial debonding in their three central stringers (see typical figures: Figs. 3-4 for COCOMAT7, and Figs. 6-7 for COCOMAT10). Debonding was introduced by inserting pieces of Teflon layers in the designated damage locations to represent the required local flaws.

The first panel among these panels to be tested was COCOMAT7. It first statically buckled at 63.8kN (single wave) and a fully developed waves pattern appeared under 102kN. Its buckling capacity compares quite well with the test results experienced by COCOMAT1-COCOMAT4 and ABAQUS prediction. However, whereas ABAQUS prediction presented an upper bound to the buckling loads observed in the tests of COCOMAT1-COCOMAT4, it is a lower bound in the case of COCOMAT7. Next the panel was cycled in the range of 0-150 kN (1.663 and 0.729 of ABAQUS predictions of buckling and collapse, respectively) during 2000 cycles, without any visible reduction

experienced in the axial stiffness. The panel completed 52k cycles in that load range, complemented by another 10k cycles in the range of 0-180kN(1.996 and 0.875 buckling and collapse loads predicted by ABAQUS, respectively) and another 1.82k cycles in the range 0-200kN(equal to 2.218 buckling and 0. 972 collapse of ABAQUS predictions) . During cycle #63,821 the panel collapsed under 158.7kN, due to a local failure of one of the stringers (for more details see [20]). One should notice that although the panel collapsed under such a relatively low load, it sustained the 200kN during its repeated loading (slightly lower as compared with the results observed in the tests of panels COCOMAT2 – COCOMAT4 and ABAQUS predictions).

Fig. 3 Locations of the strain gages and axial and lateral LVDT's – Panel COCOMAT7.

Fig. 4 Panel COCOMAT7 - Locations of the artificial damage (marked with X) (a). realization, (b). design

In light of the test results and observations on panel COCOMAT7, which did not reveal any degradation due to the artificial damage that was introduced during the manufacturing process, it was decided to introduce other damage types to amplify the influence of damage presence on the integrity of the panel and consequently its behavior. Therefore, in the tests of panels COCOMAT8 – COCOMAT10, impact was introduced into the panels, in addition to the artificial ones, in the vicinity of the artificial delamination. Typical sizes and locations are given in Fig. 5 for panel COCOMAT8. The first panel tested among that containing impact damage was COCOMAT8. Like the previous panels, panel COCOMAT8 was first statically tested and buckled under 90 kN with a fully developed waves pattern. It was found that this buckling capacity agrees well with the test results corresponding to COCOMAT2-COCOMAT7, as well as with ABAQUS predictions. Next it was repeatedly cycled in the range of 0-150 kN (equal to 1.663 and 0.729 of ABAQUS prediction of buckling and collapse, respectively) for 2000 cycles, without any visible reduction in the axial stiffness. The panel completed 50k cycles in that loading range without experiencing any reduction in its stiffness or growth in damage. Hence, the presence of the preliminary extended damage had no influence on the response of the panel, even under repeated buckling. The panel collapsed under a load of 201.1 kN, in very good agreement with the test results of COCOMAT2-COCOMAT7 and ABAQUS calculations.

Fig. 5 The locations of the strain gages, the axial and lateral LVDT's and the damage induced by the air gun (in orange)– Panel COCOMAT8.

The next panel tested was COCOMAT9. The panel was almost identical to COCOMAT8, however the shape of the impact damage and locations differed from those associated with COCOMAT8 (see also [20]). It was first statically tested and buckled at 75 kN with a single local wave. Under 90kN (which compares very well with the test results of COCOMAT2-COCOMAT4 and COCOMAT8, as well as ABAQUS predictions) almost a fully developed waves pattern was observed. Then, it was repeatedly cycled in the range of 0-150 kN (0.729 collapse predicted by ABAQUS) during 2k cycles, without observing any visible reduction in the axial stiffness. The panel was further cycled in the above load range. During cycle # 25169 the panel collapsed, probably due to the severe induced damage. It should be noted that this number of cycles is two orders higher than the expectation of reaching beyond the buckling load level during the life of the panel.

The last panel tested in the present test series, was COCOMAT10 which was similar to COCOMAT8 and COCOMAT9, however the induced damage was different (see Fig. 6). The panel was first statically tested and buckled at 73.5 kN (a single local wave) and at 103.8kN a fully developed waves pattern, in very good agreement with the test results of COCOMAT7. Next, it was repeatedly cycled in the range of 0-150 kN during 2k cycles. Again, like in the tests with COCOMAT8 and COCOMAT9 no visible reduction in the axial stiffness was observed. After completing 50k cycles in that load range, the panel was loaded till 197.9 kN (0.962 ABAQUS collapse prediction) where first collapse occurred (Fig. 7c), the axial load slightly dropped to 180kN. Further increase in the axial compression resulted in a second collapse at 229.2 kN equal to 1.114 ABAQUS collapse prediction followed by a drop in loading to 183 kN. Figures 7a-e present the development of the postbuckling wave pattern, while Figs. 7f-h shows the damage after collapse (breakage of fibers and tearing of the skin). Typical readings of the strain gages after 50k cycles as compared with the results after performing the 1st loading test are shown in Fig. 8. Almost no difference can be noted between the two tests. COCOMAT10 also exhibits the relatively large difference between buckling and collapse.

Fig. 6 The locations of the strain gages, the axial and lateral LVDT's and the damage induced by the air gun (in orange)– Panel COCOMAT10.

Fig. 7 Panel COCOMAT10 - Development of the buckling pattern as a function of axial compression : (a) under 91.8 kN, (b) under 113.8 kN, (c) under 197.9 kN, (d) under 226 kN,(e) under 229. 2 kN (f), (g),(h) damage after collapse under 229.2 kN

Fig. 8 Panel COCOMAT10: Strain gages (# 7& 8) readings vs. axial compression (1st test compared with after 50k cycles test).

CONCLUSIONS

Curved stringer-stiffened composite panels were tested under axial compression to yield the "first" buckling and postbuckling behavior till collapse. All of the panels, except one, COCOMAT2, underwent repeated cyclic postbuckling loading. Except for panel COCOMAT1, used as a reference panel, all the other seven panels had stringers without drop-off layers. Four panels contained either artificial type damage, or both artificial and impact induced damage. One of these four panels contained an artificial

delamination between the stringers and the skin, while the other three had artificial delaminations between the stringers and the skin as well as impact induced damage at the same locations. The program content and results are summarized next:

Cyclic/repeated buckling was applied well in relatively "deep" postbuckling region.

It was demonstrated that neither repeated buckling, within the number of cycles applied in the present program, and/nor the artificial damage and the induced impact damage, that were introduced into the panels, resulted in stiffness degradation of the panels.

No premature failure of any of the tested panels was observed within their expected life cycle, i.e. exposure to a few hundred of cycles deep in the postbuckling region, even in presence of either type or combination of the above damage. Only panel COCOMAT9 collapsed during repeated loading, however after 25168 cycles, i.e. by two orders higher than the anticipated exposure to higher than limit loading condition. Most of the tested panels sustained repeated postbuckling loading with more than many times the designated number of cycles within their design "life cycle" under loads significantly exceeding their limit load (first buckling) before they were subjected to static loading aimed at determining their collapse loads.

In spite of the present design, i.e. stiffeners with no drop-off plies that aimed amongst other at providing a mechanism for initiating stiffener debonding no skin-stringer separation was encountered till collapse of the panels.

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